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Anthropogenic and Domestic Waste Impacts on Surface Water Quality of Asa River, Ilorin, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Asa River, a vital freshwater source for Ilorin, faces increasing pressure from anthropogenic activities such as industrial effluents, agricultural runoff, and domestic waste discharges. This study examined spatial and temporal variations in water quality across wet and dry seasons using field surveys, laboratory analyses, and statistical tests. While most physicochemical parameters were within limits, microbial indicators consistently exceeded thresholds, posing serious health risks. Water Quality Index (WQI) assessments classified the river as poor and unsuitable for domestic use without treatment. Independent samples t-tests indicated significant upstream–downstream differences, highlighting localized pollution hotspots, while paired samples t-tests confirmed greater deterioration during the dry season due to reduced dilution. Two-way Analysis of Variance revealed significant season–location interactions for parameters such as nitrate, dissolved oxygen, and biological oxygen demand, reflecting complex pollution dynamics. Overall, the findings demonstrate severe human-driven pollution of Asa River and underscore the urgent need for stricter regulation, improved monitoring, and sustainable waste management to protect environmental and public health.

Keywords: Water Quality Assessment, Water Quality Index, Surface Water Pollution, Asa River Nigeria, Seasonal Variation

1. INTRODUCTION

Surface water quality has a direct impact on ecosystems, human health, and socioeconomic development of a community. Freshwater from rivers, streams, and lakes is

essential for many uses, such as drinking, irrigation, industrial activities, and leisure. Like many developing nations, Nigeria faces a serious environmental problem with surface water contamination, which is made worse by the country's accelerated industrialization, urbanization, and poor waste management techniques. Studies have consistently shown that anthropogenic activities lead to increased levels of pollutants, including heavy metals, nutrients, and organic matter, in surface water bodies [1, 2].

Asa River is the longest river that traverses Ilorin [3]. The river's water quality is crucial for various uses, including drinking water supply, irrigation, and recreational activities. The Asa River's water quality has been reported to be deteriorating, with high levels of pollutants and decreased water clarity [4]. This degradation poses serious health risks to humans and aquatic life, highlighting the need for urgent attention and effective management strategies. The monitoring of physical and chemical characteristics of a water body is vital for long term and short-term productivity of the water [5].

Globally, several rivers have been investigated for water quality, including the Kelani River in Sri Lanka [6], Aksu River in Turkey [7], Joanes River in Brazil [8], Lower Danube in Hungary [9], Limpopo River in South Africa [10], and Talar River in Iran [11].

Previous studies on Asa River have consistently reported significant pollution linked to industrial effluents, waste leachates, and urbanization. Adekunle et al. [12] found elevated concentrations of lead, cadmium, and mercury attributed to industrial discharge, while Oshode et al. [13] demonstrated ecotoxicological risks using fish bioassays and landfill leachate analyses.

Ajadi et al. [14] further highlighted health hazards from effluent discharges affecting communities relying on the river for agriculture and drinking water. Comparative analysis by Akinboro et al. [15] reported cadmium and other organic contaminants with cytogenotoxic effects, reinforcing concerns over ecological and human health risks. More recently, Solihu and Bilewu [4] applied the Water Quality Index (WQI) and confirmed deterioration of water quality downstream due to urban activities, concluding that the river is fit for irrigation but unsafe for drinking without treatment. Despite these efforts, there is a lack of in-depth analysis of the spatial and temporal variations of Asa River water quality.

This study addresses this gap by investigating the spatial and temporal variations in water quality parameters of Asa River, assessing the contributions of anthropogenic activities and domestic waste to water pollution, and determining the impact of pollution on aquatic life and human health. The importance of identifying the sources and causes of water pollution in Asa River cannot be overstated.

This knowledge is essential for developing targeted interventions to improve water quality and ensure the well-being of communities that depend on the river. Moreover, understanding the impact of pollution on aquatic life and human health is crucial for ensuring the long-term sustainability of Asa River's water resources.

This study investigates the impact of anthropogenic activities on the Asa River's water quality by identifying major pollution sources, determining pollutant types and concentrations, and analysing spatial and temporal variations in key physical, chemical, and biological parameters.

The Water Quality Index (WQI) was computed to assess compliance with national and international standards, while potential human health and environmental risks associated with the river's water quality were also evaluated.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Description of Study Area

The study area, Asa River, is located in Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria. The climate in Ilorin is humid tropical with distinct wet and dry seasons. The dry season lasts from November to March, whereas the wet season lasts from April to October. The city has typical temperatures between 25 and 28.9 °C and average annual rainfall of 1150 mm. Ilorin's relative humidity normally ranges from 65% to 80%.

Asa River, with a length of 56 km, originated from Oyo State, Nigeria which is the largest river that flows through the city of Ilorin in a South-North direction establishing a dividing boundary between Eastern and Western Ilorin. Asa River is about 1040 km² in area and lies between latitudes 8°36'N and 8°24'N and longitudes 4°36'E and 4°10'E [16].

Asa River has its inlet at River Awon, which is one of the tributaries of River Niger, at 12,200 m North of Ilorin. It is merged with River Imoru and to the East by River Oyun. River Asa is vital to the livelihoods of the communities that live along its banks because it supplies water for agriculture, fishing, drinking, and sanitation. Figure 1 depicts the Asa River Basin.

Figure 1. Location Asa River Basin in Ilorin metropolis [16].

2. 2. Methodology

2. 2. 1. Field Observation and Mapping

A reconnaissance survey was conducted along the Asa River to identify anthropogenic activities potentially impacting water quality. Residential, industrial, commercial, educational, and health-related establishments near the river were documented, with geographic coordinates recorded and spatially mapped using ArcGIS.

2. 2. 2. Study Design and Sampling

Four sampling points were selected along the Asa River in Ilorin, with collections carried out in the dry (November, 2024 to February, 2025) and wet (April, 2025 to July, 2025) seasons to capture seasonal variations. Their locations are shown in Figure 2, and coordinates are listed in Table 1.

Figure 2. Location of the sampling points along Asa River.

Table 1. Geographical Coordinates of the Sampling Points.

Sampling Point	Road along sampling point	Longitude	Latitude
A	Asa Dam Road	4°33'37.06"E	8°27'6.21"N
B	Unity Road	4°33'17.85"E	8°28'38.11"N
C	Emir's Road	4°33'40.15"E	8°29'16.67"N
D	Amilegbe Road	4°33'51.88"E	8°29'38.71"N

2. 2. 3. Water Sampling and Laboratory Analysis

Water samples were collected at each site using grab or composite methods with standard field meters (pH, temperature, turbidity) and GPS for location. Samples were stored in sterile containers on ice and transported within six hours to the Central Research and Analytical Laboratory, Ilorin, for analysis. All tests were carried out according to United States Environmental Protection Agency [17].

2. 2. 4. Statistical Analysis

Various inferential statistical techniques were employed in this study. The independent samples t-test was used to determine significant differences in mean parameter concentrations between the upstream and downstream sections of the river, with the null hypothesis assuming no difference. The paired samples t-test compared water quality parameters at the same sampling sites across dry and wet seasons, assessing whether observed seasonal differences were statistically significant. A two-way ANOVA evaluated the effects of season (dry vs. wet) and location (upstream vs. downstream) on water quality parameters, including their interaction effects. Interaction effects were critical to understanding whether seasonal influences varied by location.

2. 2. 5. Comparison of measured parameters with standards

In this study, the measured parameters were evaluated against the World Health Organization guidelines [18] and the Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality [19]. For ease of reference, these will be referred subsequently as the WHO standard and the NSDWQ standard, respectively. Table 2 presents the concentration limits of water quality parameters of both WHO and NSDWQ standards.

In order to properly visualize the disparity of each parameter from the standard values, the exceedance values are obtained through equation 1. This technique normalizes all values to a common benchmark.

$$Exceedance\ Ratio = \frac{Measured\ Value}{Standard\ Limit} \tag{1}$$

Exceedance value $\begin{cases} < 1; \text{parameter within standard limit} \\ > 1; \text{parameter above standard limit} \end{cases}$

Table 2. Acceptable concentration limits of water quality parameters of WHO and NSDWQ standards.

Nature	Parameter	WHO	NSDWQ
Physical	pH	6.5 - 8.5	6.5 - 8.5
	Temperature (°C)	28	Ambient (32 °C)
	Turbidity (NTU)	5	5
	Colour (TCU)	2	15
	Total dissolved solids (mg/L)	600	500
Chemical	Biological oxygen demand , BOD (mg/L)	10	10
	Dissolved oxygen, DO (mg/L)	5	5
	Nitrate (NO ₃ ⁻) (mg/L)	50	50
	Nitrite (NO ₂ ⁻) (mg/L)	3	0.2
	Phosphate (mg/L)	NS	NS
	Nitrogen (mg/L)	NS	NS
	Lead (mg/L)	0.01	0.01
	Iron (mg/L)	0.3	0.3
	Copper (mg/L)	2	1
	Zinc (mg/L)	3	3
	Manganese (mg/L)	0.4	0.2
Microbial	Total Coliforms (CFU/100 mL)	0	10
	Faecal Coliform (CFU/100 mL)	0	1
	Escherichia coli, E. coli (CFU/100 mL)	0	1

2. 2. 6. Geospatial Analysis

This was to reveal the spatial distribution of the observed water quality parameters. The interpolation tool in ArcGIS was employed for this operation. Spatial interpolation is able to predict the value of attributes at unsampled sites from measurements made at point locations within the same area. There are several mathematical methods to complete the spatial interpolation process, such as Kriging, Inverse Distance Weighted (IDW), Natural Neighbour,

Spline, Trend, etc. However, the Kriging and IDW technique are widely used in environmental studies [20]. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) recognized that Kriging would be a more accurate option [17]. Nas et al. [21] and Balakrishnan et al. [22] achieved the best results using the Kriging method. Based on this, the Kriging method was employed in this study.

2. 3. Water Quality Index

Water Quality Index (WQI) is a common method used to assess the impact of anthropogenic activities by monitoring physicochemical and microbiological variables. Environmental assessments often accompany WQI to provide a comprehensive understanding of water quality changes due to human activities. The water quality index (WQI) serves as a simple tool for evaluating the fundamental water resource in public policy decision-making processes and in monitoring its impacts.

The WQI concept was introduced long ago in Germany, and since then, numerous modifications of WQI have been introduced by researchers, and comparisons of the different modifications exist in the scientific literature [23]. Although there are many WQIs available worldwide, none is universally accepted due to the difference in climate and land use [23]. The two WQI methods employed in this study are enumerated below.

2. 3. 1. Weighted Average Water Quality Index

WA-WQI takes into account the level of toxicity and impact of each observed parameter by assigning different weights to the parameters [9]. A setback of WA-WQI is the high sensitivity to certain parameters with very high concentrations which overly shoot up the final WQI value [24]. Calmuc et al. [9] recommends the use of WA-WQI with other WQI indices. Table 3 outlines water quality classification based on WA-WQI.

Table 3. WA-WQI Classification [10].

Water Quality Index (WQI) Range	Water Classification
< 50	Excellent
50 – 100	Good water
100 – 200	Poor water
200 – 300	Very poor water
> 300	Unfit for use

The procedure for computing the WA-WQI is detailed in Equations 2–5, as described by Bora and Goswami [25]:

$$WQI_{WA} = \frac{\sum Q_n W_n}{\sum W_n} \tag{2}$$

where: WQI_{WA} is WQI based on the weighted average method, Q_n is the quality rating of nth water quality parameter, W_n is the unit weight of nth water quality parameter.

The quality rating, Q_n is calculated using the equation:

$$Q_n = 100 \left[\frac{V_n - V_i}{V_s - V_i} \right] \tag{3}$$

where: V_n is the actual amount of nth parameter present, V_i is the ideal value of the parameter [$V_i = 0$, except for pH ($V_i = 7$) and DO ($V_i = 14.6 \text{ mg/l}$)], V_s is the standard permissible value for the nth water quality parameter.

Unit weight (W_n) is calculated using the formula:

$$W_n = \frac{K}{V_s} \tag{4}$$

where: k is the constant of proportionality and it is calculated using the equation:

$$k = [1/\sum 1/V_s, s = 1,2, \dots, n] \tag{5}$$

2. 3. 2. Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment Water Quality Index

The Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment (CCME) developed the CCME WQI. Unlike WA-WQI, weights are not assigned in CCME WQI. However, CCME WQI is based on a combination of the number of parameters whose guidelines are not met (scope), the frequency with which the guidelines are not met (frequency), and the amount by which the guidelines are not met (amplitude). The procedure for CCME-WQI computation is outlined in [26]. Table 4 presents the CCME-WQI water classification.

Table 4. CCME-WQI Index Classification (Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment [26]).

CCME-WQI Value	Rating	Remarks
95–100	Excellent	Water quality is protected with a virtual absence of threat or impairment; conditions very close to natural or pristine levels.
80–94	Good	Water quality is protected, with only a minor degree of impairment, and conditions rarely departing from natural or desirable level.
65–79	Fair	Water quality is usually protected, but occasionally impaired, and conditions which sometimes depart from natural or desirable level.
45–64	Marginal	Water quality is frequently threatened or impaired and conditions often departing from natural or desirable level.

CCME-WQI Value	Rating	Remarks
0–44	Poor	Water quality is almost always threatened or impaired and conditions usually departing from natural or desirable level.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. Concentrations of Water Quality Parameters

Table 5 presents the mean concentrations of the water quality parameters for the four sites for both dry and wet seasons.

Table 5. Mean concentrations of the water quality parameters for both dry and wet seasons.

Parameter	Dry Season				Wet Season			
	Upstream		Downstream		Upstream		Downstream	
	A	B	C	D	A	B	C	D
pH	8.26	8.10	8.01	8.08	7.91	7.96	5.05	7.31
Temperature	28.03	27.73	28.10	27.65	29.13	29.03	29.10	29.05
Turbidity	4.86	4.41	5.07	4.64	3.39	2.75	3.73	2.46
Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)	177.50	270.00	355.00	77.50	369.50	268.75	330.75	90.50
Colour	3.03	2.75	3.17	2.90	2.12	1.72	2.33	1.48
Nitrate	0.46	0.46	0.46	0.48	0.25	0.27	0.27	0.23
Nitrite	0.21	0.23	0.26	0.22	0.07	0.06	0.07	0.06
Phosphate	1.11	1.12	1.08	1.05	0.06	0.04	0.13	0.56
Lead (Pb)	4.71	12.01	6.84	8.85	0.12	0.01	0.10	0.03
Copper (Cu)	0.85	1.00	1.34	0.67	0.17	0.15	0.20	0.14
Manganese (Mn)	0.50	0.33	0.50	0.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Zinc (Zn)	4.84	5.69	6.18	4.34	1.41	1.10	1.28	1.16
Iron (Fe)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	5.09	5.59	3.15	4.94
Nitrogen	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.02

Parameter	Dry Season				Wet Season			
	Upstream		Downstream		Upstream		Downstream	
	A	B	C	D	A	B	C	D
Dissolved Oxygen (DO)	4.73	4.93	5.18	4.75	4.50	3.97	3.90	3.90
Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD)	0.78	1.43	0.95	0.73	1.63	0.65	0.43	0.20
Total Coliforms, TC ($\times 10^5$)	30.25	150.25	119.25	87.00	150.25	64.50	190.75	51.00
Faecal Coliform, FC	18.25	55.50	50.50	33.50	20.25	49.00	52.00	33.50
<i>Escherichia coli</i> , <i>E. coli</i>	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

* Units: Temperature (°C), Turbidity (NTU), TC, FC, and *E. coli* are in CFU/100 mL, other parameters are in mg/L.

3. 2. Comparison of Parameters Concentration with Water Quality Standards

The comparison of measured parameters with permissible limits set by standards provides a general and quick assessment of the Asa River's water quality. Tables 6 and 7 presents the exceedance results for dry and wet seasons respectively. Phosphate and nitrogen were excluded from the analysis because no recommended limits were provided by both WHO and NSDWQ standards.

Table 6. Exceedance values of measured parameters for dry season.

Parameter	WHO Exceedance				NSDWQ Exceedance			
	Upstream		Downstream		Upstream		Downstream	
	A	B	C	D	A	B	C	D
pH	0.97	0.95	0.94	0.95	0.97	0.95	0.94	0.95
Temp.	1.00	0.99	1.00	0.99	0.88	0.87	0.88	0.86
Turbidity	0.97	0.88	1.01	0.93	0.97	0.88	1.01	0.93
TDS	0.30	0.45	0.59	0.13	0.36	0.54	0.71	0.16
Colour	0.20	0.18	0.21	0.19	0.20	0.18	0.21	0.19

Parameter	WHO Exceedance				NSDWQ Exceedance			
	Upstream		Downstream		Upstream		Downstream	
	A	B	C	D	A	B	C	D
Nitrate	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
Nitrite	0.07	0.08	0.09	0.07	1.05	1.15	1.30	1.10
Pb	471.00	1201.00	684.00	885.00	471.00	1201.00	684.00	885.00
Cu	0.43	0.50	0.67	0.34	0.85	1.00	1.34	0.67
Mn	1.25	0.83	1.25	1.25	2.50	1.65	2.50	2.50
Zn	1.61	1.90	2.06	1.45	1.61	1.90	2.06	1.45
Fe	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
DO	1.06	1.01	0.97	1.05	1.10	1.00	1.00	1.10
BOD	0.08	0.14	0.10	0.07	0.08	0.14	0.10	0.07
TC	3.03×10^9	1.50×10^{10}	1.19×10^{10}	8.70×10^9	3.03×10^5	1.50×10^6	1.19×10^6	8.70×10^5
FC	1.83×10^4	5.55×10^9	5.05×10^9	3.35×10^9	18.30	55.50	50.50	33.50
<i>E. coli</i>	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

* Units: Temperature (°C), Turbidity (NTU), TC, FC, and *E. coli* are in CFU/100 mL, other parameters are in mg/L.

** Key

	<1		1		>1
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Table 7. Exceedance values of measured parameters for wet season.

Parameter	WHO Exceedance				NSDWQ Exceedance			
	Upstream		Downstream		Upstream		Downstream	
	A	B	C	D	A	B	C	D
pH	0.93	0.94	0.59	0.86	0.93	0.94	0.59	0.86
Temp.	1.04	1.04	1.04	1.04	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.91
Turbidity	0.68	0.55	0.75	0.49	0.68	0.55	0.75	0.49
TDS	0.62	0.45	0.55	0.15	0.74	0.54	0.66	0.18

Parameter	WHO Exceedance				NSDWQ Exceedance			
	Upstream		Downstream		Upstream		Downstream	
	A	B	C	D	A	B	C	D
Colour	0.14	0.11	0.16	0.10	0.14	0.11	0.16	0.10
Nitrate	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.00
Nitrite	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.35	0.30	0.35	0.30
Pb	12.00	1.00	10.00	3.00	12.00	1.00	10.00	3.00
Cu	0.09	0.08	0.10	0.07	0.17	0.15	0.20	0.14
Mn	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Zn	0.47	0.37	0.43	0.39	0.47	0.37	0.43	0.39
Fe	16.97	18.63	10.50	16.47	16.97	18.63	10.50	16.47
DO	0.90	0.79	0.78	0.78	0.90	0.79	0.78	0.78
BOD	0.16	0.07	0.04	0.02	0.16	0.07	0.04	0.02
TC	4.5×10^8	6.45×10^9	1.91×10^{10}	5.1×10^9	4.5×10^4	6.45×10^5	1.91×10^6	5.1×10^5
FC	2.03×10^4	4.90×10^4	5.20×10^4	3.35×10^4	20.25	49.00	52.00	33.50
<i>E. coli</i>	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

* Units: Temperature (°C), Turbidity (NTU), TC, FC, and *E. coli* are in CFU/100 mL, other parameters are in mg/L.

** Key

	<1		1		>1
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The pH, colour, TDS, BOD, and nitrate concentrations were all within the permissible limits set by both WHO and NSDWQ standards across the dry and wet seasons. In few cases, temperature and turbidity were slightly above the limits, Dissolved oxygen (DO), being a peculiar parameter, is expected to remain above the minimum standard. In the dry season, only site C did not meet the required WHO limit, while in the wet season, none of the sites met both WHO and NSDWQ acceptable limits. Zinc exceeded the standards in the dry season but remained within permissible levels during the wet season. Nitrite exhibited high exceedance values when assessed against the NSDWQ standard, primarily due to the relatively lower threshold prescribed by the guideline. However, the concentrations remained within the permissible limits established by the WHO standard. Copper exceeded the limits in few cases in the dry season while it remained within the permissible limits in the wet season. Manganese and iron were only detected in dry and wet seasons respectively, and in those cases, their concentrations surpassed the allowable limits. Lead, total coliforms, and faecal coliforms

extremely exceeded the permissible limits in both seasons, highlighting significant water quality concerns.

3. 3. Water Quality Index (WQI)

Table 8 presents the summary of the CCME-WQI and WA-WQI results for the four scenarios (Dry-Upstream, Dry-Downstream, Wet-Upstream, Wet-Downstream) of WQI analysis using both WHO and NSDWQ standards. Phosphate and Nitrogen were excluded from the analysis because no recommended limits were provided by both WHO and NSDWQ standards. Similarly, E. coli was excluded since it was undetected in both seasons.

Table 8. Summary of WQI results.

Location	Dry Season				Wet Season			
	CCME-WQI		WA-WQI		CCME-WQI		WA-WQI	
	WHO	NSDWQ	WHO	NSDWQ	WHO	NSDWQ	WHO	NSDWQ
Upstream (Sites A & B)	33.91	31.14	84.73	105.27	36.35	37.80	62.76	34.28
	(Poor)	(Poor)	(Good)	(Poor)	(Poor)	(Poor)	(Good)	(Poor)
Downstream (Sites C & D)	32.20	29.57	85.86	113.77	34.70	36.35	53.75	31.96
	(Poor)	(Poor)	(Good)	(Poor)	(Poor)	(Poor)	(Good)	(Poor)

From Table 8, based on the CCME-WQI method, the water quality of Asa River under all scenarios is classified as Poor using both the WHO and NSDWQ standard. However, under the WA-WQI method, the water is classified as Poor using the NSDWQ standard and Good using the WHO standard. This implies that WA-WQI approach is influenced by the type of standard employed in computing the WQI unlike the CCME-WQI. This aligns with the findings of Calmuc et al. [9], who reported that WA-WQI is more strongly influenced by parameters with low permissible thresholds compared to CCME-WQI. Taking this fact into account, it is safe to conclude that the water quality of Asa River is poor.

3. 4. Independent samples t-tests (Upstream vs Downstream)

Independent samples t-tests were conducted to examine whether water quality parameters differed significantly between upstream and downstream locations as shown in Table 9.

The independent samples t-tests (Table 9) examined whether there were significant differences in water quality parameters between upstream and downstream sites. Most parameters showed no significant variation, suggesting that pollution sources are fairly distributed along the river. However, some critical exceptions were observed. pH was significantly lower downstream ($p = 0.007$), reflecting increased acidic input likely due to industrial or domestic discharges. Nitrogen levels also showed a significant difference

($p = 0.002$), indicating potential localized nutrient enrichment. Importantly, BOD values were significantly lower downstream ($p \approx 0.001$), contrasting with the expected pattern of higher organic load downstream and suggesting possible dilution effects in the lower reaches. These findings imply that while many pollutants are evenly distributed, certain parameters point to localized hotspots of contamination.

Table 9. Independent samples t-test result.

Parameter	Mean (Upstream)	Mean (Downstream)	p-value	Interpretation
pH	8.05	7.11	0.007	Significantly lower downstream
Temp.	28.48	28.48	1.000	Not significant
Turbidity	3.85	3.97	0.712	Not significant
TDS	271.44	213.44	0.159	Not significant
Colour	2.4	2.47	0.761	Not significant
Nitrate	0.36	0.36	0.992	Not significant
Nitrite	0.14	0.15	0.684	Not significant
Phosphate	0.58	0.7	0.478	Not significant
Pb	4.21	3.95	0.875	Not significant
Cu	0.54	0.58	0.799	Not significant
Mn	0.21	0.25	0.629	Not significant
Zinc	3.26	3.24	0.975	Not significant
Iron	2.67	2.02	0.476	Not significant
Nitrogen	0	0.01	0.002	Significantly higher downstream
DO	4.53	4.43	0.577	Not significant
BOD	1.12	0.58	0.000	Significantly lower downstream
TC	98.81	112.00	0.495	Not significant
FC	35.75	42.38	0.188	Not significant

3. 5. Paired samples t-tests (Dry vs Wet Seasons)

Paired samples t-tests were conducted to assess seasonal variations in water quality parameters between the dry and wet seasons and the results presented in Table 10.

Table 10. Paired samples t-test result.

Parameter	Mean (Dry Season)	Mean (Wet Season)	p-value	Interpretation
pH	8.11	7.05	0.202	Not significant
Temperature	27.88	29.08	0.001	Significantly higher in the wet season
Turbidity	4.74	3.08	0.003	Significantly lower in the wet season
TDS	220	264.88	0.433	Not significant
Colour	2.96	1.91	0.004	Significantly lower in the wet season
Nitrate	0.47	0.26	0.001	Significantly lower in the wet season
Nitrite	0.23	0.06	0.000	Significantly lower in the wet season
Phosphate	1.09	0.2	0.007	Significantly lower in the wet season
Lead	8.1	0.07	0.015	Significantly lower in the wet season
Copper	0.97	0.16	0.009	Significantly lower in the wet season
Manganese	0.46	0	0.002	Significantly lower in the wet season
Zinc	5.26	1.23	0.002	Significantly lower in the wet season
Iron	0	4.69	0.003	Significantly higher in the wet season
Nitrogen	0	0.01	0.302	Not significant
DO	4.89	4.07	0.033	Significantly lower in the wet season
BOD	0.97	0.73	0.556	Not significant
TC	96.69	114.13	0.737	Not significant
FC	39.44	38.69	0.728	Not significant

The paired samples t-tests (Table 10) revealed clear seasonal variation. Parameters such as turbidity ($p = 0.003$), nitrate ($p = 0.001$), nitrite ($p = 0.001$), phosphate ($p = 0.007$), lead ($p = 0.015$), copper ($p = 0.009$), manganese ($p = 0.002$), and zinc ($p = 0.002$) were significantly lower in the wet season, consistent with dilution effects from rainfall and increased flow. BOD did not indicate a significant difference between the two seasons whereas DO ($p = 0.033$) was significantly lower in the wet season. Similarly, iron increased significantly in the wet season ($p = 0.003$), which may be linked to runoff from surrounding soils or erosion.

3. 6. Two-way Analysis of Variance (Season-Location Interaction)

The Two-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was conducted to assess the influence of the both season and location simultaneously on the water quality parameters. The results are presented in Table 11.

Table 11. Two-way ANOVA (Season-Location Interaction).

Parameters	Season Effect (p-value)	Location Effect (p-value)	Season-Location Interaction (p-value)
pH	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
Temperature	<0.001	1	1
Turbidity	<0.001	0.43	0.54
TDS	0.266	0.153	0.212
Colour	<0.001	0.523	0.447
Nitrate	<0.001	0.937	0.014
Nitrite	<0.001	0.006	0.009
Phosphate	<0.001	0.006	<0.001
Lead	<0.001	0.723	0.723
Copper	<0.001	0.545	0.646
Manganese	<0.001	0.013	0.013
Zinc	<0.001	0.903	0.941
Iron	<0.001	0.017	0.018
Nitrogen	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
DO	<0.001	0.204	0.004
BOD	0.046	<0.001	0.023
TC	0.378	0.504	0.987
FC	0.884	0.202	0.77

The two-way ANOVA (Table 11) highlighted the combined effects of season and location on Asa River water quality. Parameters such as pH, nitrate, nitrite, phosphate, iron, manganese, nitrogen, DO, and BOD exhibited significant season–location interactions, showing that

pollution intensity was not uniform but varied depending on both where and when the samples were collected. For example, nitrate concentrations were more pronounced upstream during the wet season but shifted downstream in the dry season, reflecting complex pollution dynamics.

Dissolved oxygen was consistently lower downstream in both seasons, while BOD levels were unexpectedly higher upstream, suggesting localized organic loading. These results underscore the influence of effluent discharge points and hydrological changes on pollution patterns in Asa River.

3. 7. Spatial and Seasonal Variations of Water Quality Parameters

Scatter plots and GIS spatial maps are presented together for six vital parameters for easy visualization of the distribution of water quality parameters across the spatial and temporal groups which are dry season upstream (Dry US), dry season downstream (Dry DS), wet season upstream (Wet US), and wet season downstream (Wet DS) along the Asa River. No scatter plot or spatial map was presented for E.coli since it was undetected in both seasons.

Figure 3. Seasonal and Spatial Variation of pH in Asa River.

Figure 4. Seasonal and Spatial Variation of temperature in Asa River.

Figure 5. Seasonal and Spatial Variation of BOD in Asa River.

Figure 6. Seasonal and Spatial Variation of DO in Asa River.

Figure 7. Seasonal and Spatial Variation of lead in Asa River.

Figure 8. Seasonal and Spatial Variation of iron in Asa River.

The pH of Asa River was predominantly alkaline (7.9–8.4), except in the downstream section during the wet season, where it declined to an average of 6.2, indicating acidic conditions (Figure 3a). This seasonal decline is likely linked to rainfall and runoff transporting acidic inputs such as organic matter, industrial effluents, and agricultural residues. Similar patterns were reported by Solihu and Bilewu [4] and Ahaneku and Animashaun [27] who observed upstream–downstream pH values ranging from 6.8 to 9.7. Although pH has limited direct health impacts [28], it strongly influences aquatic ecosystems, with the optimal range for most species being 6.5–8.5. Spatial map (Figure 3b) showed alkaline conditions across the river during the dry season, while the wet season revealed lower pH values, particularly downstream.

Water temperature ranged from 27.4–29.2 °C during the dry season and was generally higher in the wet season (Figure 4a). The overall mean of 28.5 °C is consistent with 28.01 °C previously reported for Asa River [27], though slightly higher than the 24 °C reported by Solihu and Bilewu [4], where seasonal context was not specified. Spatial distribution (Figure 4b) showed that in both seasons, the central stretch (site B) recorded the highest temperatures, with values declining upstream and downstream. This consistent spatial gradient suggests localized thermal influences, possibly linked to reduced shading or anthropogenic activities along the mid-river section.

BOD ranged from 0.80–1.20 mg/L in the dry season and 0.30–1.15 mg/L in the wet season (Figure 5a). Spatially (Figure 5b), dry-season BOD was higher in southern sites, while wet-season values peaked upstream (B) and declined downstream, likely reflecting localized organic pollution. DO concentrations were 4.75–5.00 mg/L in the dry season and 3.80–4.30 mg/L in the wet season (Figure 6a). Lower DO downstream, consistent with [27], suggests oxygen depletion from effluent discharges. Spatial maps (Figure 6b) showed generally moderate to low DO, with localised peaks at site C in the dry season and site B in the wet season, highlighting the influence of rainfall dilution and site-specific loading.

Lead concentrations were highest during the dry season (7.84–8.43 mg/L) and upstream in the wet season, while downstream values were low (Figure 7a). Spatially (Figure 7b), lead hotspots shifted from site A in the dry season to sites B and C in the wet season, reflecting seasonal pollutant transport. Iron was very low in the dry season but rose sharply in the wet season (4.05–5.32 mg/L), especially upstream, suggesting runoff-driven enrichment (Figure 8).

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the water quality of Asa River in Ilorin, Kwara State, focusing on how human activities influence its spatial and temporal variations. Through field observations, laboratory tests, and statistical analyses, it was found that pollutant concentrations fluctuate seasonally, with peaks during the wet season attributed to increased runoff and stormwater inputs.

Despite many physical and chemical parameters meeting national and international standards, microbial levels significantly exceeded permissible limits, raising serious health concerns. WQI assessments indicated a generally poor classification for the river, with both CCME-WQI and WA-WQI underscoring the degraded state. Seasonal and locational analyses using statistical tests showcased significant variations in water quality, with higher pollutant concentrations during the dry season due to reduced rainfall dilution.

The findings highlight that human activities, including industrial discharge and inadequate waste management, substantially impact the water quality of Asa River. Seasonal fluctuations and localized pollution hotspots complicate the water quality landscape, with particular concern for the dry season when pollution levels rise. This study emphasizes the urgent need for improved pollution management strategies to safeguard public health and preserve the river's ecosystem.

Based on the findings, key interventions for restoring Asa River include the establishment of centralized waste collection and treatment facilities near the river and the enforcement of functional effluent treatment plants for industries with strict compliance to Environmental Impact Assessment regulations. Public education on pollution impacts and community participation in river protection are essential, alongside regular monitoring, audits, and the imposition of stricter penalties for non-compliance. Finally, developing collaborative frameworks between government, industries, and local communities is crucial to achieving sustainable river restoration and protection.

This study provides a comprehensive inferential statistical assessment of Asa River, showing the spatial, seasonal, and interaction effects in water quality parameters. Further studies should extend monitoring periods to capture long-term trends, assess pollutant accumulation in sediments, and integrate hydrological models to simulate runoff and pollutant transport. Research should also explore climate change impacts on water quality and the socio-economic costs of Asa River pollution.

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